

Cooperative Instructional Strategy and Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance in Essay Writing in Bayelsa State

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Abstract

The study investigated cooperative instructional strategy and senior secondary school students' performance in essay writing in Bayelsa State. The study was guided with two objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses. The study adopted pre- test post- test quasi- experimental research design. The population for this study was comprised of all nineteen thousand two hundred and eighty two (19,282) senior secondary two (SS2) students in the 319 government secondary schools in Bayelsa State. A simple random sampling technique was used to select 1 local government area while a stratified random sampling technique was used in selecting 100 students from two schools made up of 58 males and 42 females for the study. A pre test of Essay Writing Performance Test (EWPT) was given to all the students before the treatment. Thereafter, the experimental group was subjected to treatment. The instrument for the data collection was Essay Writing Performance Test (EWPT) which was used to determine the academic performance of the students. In testing the reliability, the initial and re-test scores were correlated using Pearson product moment correlation and the reliability coefficient of 0.76 was obtained. The mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels. The findings revealed that cooperative instructional strategy was more effective than discussion method. Based on the findings, it is recommended that the curriculum developers should consider adopting cooperative instructional strategy to prescribe activities for content delivery in English language.

Keywords: Cooperative Instructional Strategy, English Language, Essay Writing and Learning Techniques.

Introduction

People write mainly in English in Nigeria which is the language of instructions, media, commerce and industry. Most students graduate from secondary schools without a good knowledge of English language, especially in essay writing. This is because the teachers and students do not give maximums attention and interest to developing writing good essays. Although, the English language plays a major role in the secondary school curriculum and it is obvious that some students lack the basic writing skills. However, proficiency in English language is necessary for anybody

seeking employment in an international firm or multinational companies and to improve skills needed to operate on the job.

A report on Nigerian education by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) as cited in Oyeike (2016), explained that the broad aim of secondary education within the overall national objectives is the preparation for useful living within the society and higher education. Secondary education should equip students to live effectively in the modern age of science and technology, raise a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others; respect the dignity of labour and live as good citizens; foster the Nigerian unity with an emphasis on the common ties that unite within diversity; and foster the desire for achievement and self improvement. With respect to curriculum adopted to achieve this aim, the same report stated that the English language is the most important subject. The reason for this is instantly obvious considering the fact that all other subjects, except the three indigenous languages (Igbo, Yoruba and Hausa) are taught in English. Consequently, students are expected to acquire adequate knowledge of the language and have a sound command of the four basic communication skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing) before advancing to institutions of higher learning.

Writing is one of the language skills that enable learners to respond to academic discipline. The study of English language is long life process and a great part of personal development which is beyond the classroom. According to Brown (2015), writing is the outcome of someone's thought, drafting, and revising procedures that require specialised skills. However, not everyone can develop these skills naturally. This means that one must be taught how to write in order to develop good writing skills. Writing is a straight forward way of practicing and using language outside the classroom. Learning to writing may fulfill professional needs for students after school because students may have to write business letters, emails or report in English language. So, students ought to learn how to write by practicing writing to improve their writing skills.

A regular practice of writing exercise in all subjects and good guidance on the writing exercise helps students to become good writers. There are different ways and types of writing. For examples, we have the narrative, descriptive, expository, imaginative and argumentative or persuasive writing. Each of these writings has different approaches and teaching procedures. Writing has been noted to go through three stages known as pre-writing, writing and post- writing or editing. Pre- writing is planning and organizing the work. While writing is a careful choice of vocabulary, grammatical patterns and sentence structures appropriate to the subject matter.

However, it is the role of teacher to guide the students through writing. Writing essay should be taught in classrooms through a range of fun activities and tasks. The aim of the teacher should be to help the students to write a piece of communication to link and develop ideas, information or arguments for a particular audience. The teacher has the sole role to analyse the features of written work which are: getting the grammar right, spelling correctly, using word banks, punctuate meaningfully, good sentence structures, linking ideas and information to develop a topic and

organise ideas clearly. It is obvious that students are more likely to write effectively when they are provided all the necessary guidelines as mentioned above.

In the first year in secondary school most children have little or no mastery of the English language rules. Therefore, a lot need to be done by the teacher in order to develop their writing skills. In teaching these new students, teachers should be careful not to bore or make them loose interest in learning English. It is of importance that the teachers keep themselves abreast with innovations and current trends in the field of language teaching. According to Johnson and Johnson (2008), the traditional “chalk and talk” approach of teaching is now getting inferior results when compared with the more modern and revolutionary teaching approaches that are available for use in schools today. Students’ interaction is greatly required in today’s teaching and should be encouraged.

Lack of practice is one of the problems of students’ poor writing ability. Hence, more writing practices in the classroom and at home should be enforced. This will expose the students to develop good writing skills and also lead the teacher to the student’s weak point in order to help the students. Another problem is lack of interest in reading. Students should be encouraged to reading so as to gain wider vocabulary and knowledge to enrich their work.

Ikota (2014) noted that much reading by students lead to high interest in writing which will improve the students’ communicative competence by providing them with vocabularies, ideas, structures, experiences and situations to strengthen their writing. Writing is seen as a social and cultural event. According to Weigle as cited in Daniel, (2021) writing is social because it is done in a social environment; what people write, how they write, and who they write to is affected and mould by social interaction. All over the world, people write and what they write mirror their way of life. Ashlen (2017) noted that there may be some cultural differences in people writing in respect to discourse and structure. He also went ahead to say that the male gender write differently from the female gender. This is as a result of their experiences and the things that happen to them. Brown (2015) noted that learners of English pre- dominantly structure their writing from native languages. Thus learners think in their native languages in line with their personal experiences be it male or female before putting their thought down on paper.

The concept of learning is very important and central in education. This is because all that go on in the school is an attempt to create a conducive learning environment, an environment that will facilitate and enhance students’ ability to learn. The academic achievement of students is reflective of the quality of learning they are exposed to. Educationists agreed that an individual is the by-product of both heredity and the environment. This means that the performance of student is determined by both heredity and environmental factors. It is also observable that teaching and learning are inseparable (Okoro, 2016).

According to Rao (2014) as cited in Ijoko (2021), described teaching methods are sources of revolution associated with social and cultural changes. This explains the fact that, students learn in various ways which are influenced by their individual styles and strategies. Some prefer group work while others enjoy individual work. Andermam (2017) emphasised that some students learn better through teacher instruction with worksheet and firm directions than self generated research

projects. He is of the view that the various learning strategies a student adopts is related to the type of learning environment he or she is exposed to. The learning environment affects the learners' ability and motivation to learn.

As was mentioned earlier, teaching method used by teachers determine the type of learning strategy adopted by the learners. The learner may learn through memorization, peer group interaction, individual effort and problem- solving technique. Learning strategies have been classified into the following: collaborative strategy, cooperative strategy, competitive strategy, and independent study, lecture method, etc (Ijoko, 2021).

Cooperative instructional strategy is an instructional method in which students work in small groups to accomplish a common learning goal under the guidance of the teacher. Cooperative learning strategies are content- free structures that can be reused in different school contexts. Cooperative learning is a successful teaching strategy in which small teams, each with students of different levels of ability, use a variety of learning activities to improve their understanding of the subject.

There are so many types of cooperative instructional strategies but emphasis is on group-based cooperative learning strategy. In group-based cooperative strategy, the students learn in peer. The peer groups gather together over the long term (e.g. over the course of a year, or several years such as in high school or post-secondary studies) to develop and contribute to one another's knowledge mastery on a topic by regularly discussing material, encouraging one another, and supporting the academic and personal success of group members (Oyeike, 2016). Johnson, Johnson and Holubec (2013) described this type of cooperative learning strategy as when small group of students work together to maximize content delivery. It is an instructional programme in which students work in small groups to help one another master academic content. The ideas that student learn more by doing something active than by simply watching and listening has long been known to both cognitive, psychologists and effective teachers.

On the other hand, discussion method is a variety of forums for open- ended, collaborative exchange of ideas among a teacher and students or among students for the purpose of furthering students thinking, learning, problem solving, understanding, or literary appreciation. The discussion method makes itself amenable to the teaching of variety of contents in diverse subject area. Arrangement could be concluded for the entire class to participate in a discussion; the class can also be divided into small groups. It is also possible to arrange for panel discussion. The discussion provides for students' involvement, which in turn helps to stimulate and reinforce learning.

On this note, Mezieobi (2017) opined that cooperative learning is an active learning strategy. Beyond that, cooperation enhances learning in several ways. Weak students working individually are likely to give up when they get stuck but working cooperatively, they keep going. Strong students are faced with task of explaining and clarifying material to weaker students who often find out gaps in their own understanding and fill them. Students working alone may tend to delay completing assignment or skipping them all together, but when they know that others are counting

on them. They are motivated to do the work in a timely manner. From the above, it is obvious that students learn more when they actively participate in the class than to be an observer in the classroom. Teachers should adopt diverse and new trends in teaching so as to produce good results. Kolawole (2017) investigated the effects of cooperative and competitive learning on academic performance of students in mathematics to find out which of them is more effective learning strategy. Students sample for the study was 400 senior secondary school 2Mathematics students made up of 240 boys and 160 girls randomly selected from four out five states in South West Nigeria. The finding revealed that cooperative learning strategies are more effective than competitive learning strategies. However, the present study investigated cooperative instructional strategy and senior secondary school performance in essay writing in Bayelsa State.

In a study carried out by Uzoegwu (2014) on effect of cooperative learning method on students' achievement in English essay writing in Nsukka. A quasi experiment research design, including non- equivalent control group design was used. Eight intact classes were used for the study. The sample comprised 299 students. Four research questions and seven null- hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The instrument for data collection was an essay topic. The data collected were analyzed using the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The major findings were that there was a significant effect of cooperative learning method on the students' achievement in essay writing in the English language. There was also a significant effect of cooperative method on gender in the students' achievement score in essay writing and there was no significant interaction effect of instruction method and gender, method and location and method and ability. This literature is of interest to this research because both select the same variables. The population of the previous study was drawn from the secondary schools just like the present study. The same instrument for data collection was used for the study. The research designs for both studies are equally similar. The previous research looked at Nsukka LGA in Enugu state, but the present study is in Bayelsa state.

Nnamdi (2015) carried out a study on the role of gender in cooperative learning strategy on students' academic performance in essay writing in Isiala Ngwa South local government of Abia State. He deduced that there is no significance difference in the mean performance score of both male and female high achievers in essay writing. He further observed that there is a significance difference in the mean performance score of the male and female low achievers exposed to cooperative learning method and those exposed to conventional method in essay writing. The study also observed that the mean performance scores of male students are higher than those of female students. However, there is no significance difference in the retention level of high and low achievers when exposed to cooperative learning method and when exposed to conventional method in reading. However, while the study was in Isiala Ngwa South local government of Abia State the present study is Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

Poor performance in English language at the secondary and even tertiary levels is an issue of concern in the Nigeria educational system. The most noticeable indication of under- performance is in the WAEC conducted SSCE English examination. The WAEC chief examiners' report each year confirms this. In 2018, the report stated that: "This paper was well within the experience of the candidates and the standard in the previous years; the candidates' performance however was generally disappointing. The use of conventional method is prominent in all the secondary schools in Bayelsa State. This teaching method is associated with some obvious problems. Conventional method is not capable of exposing students to enough areas in the subject matter learnt as to equip them for success. In the bid to cover the scheme, subject matters are learnt scanty and the result is usually a poor performance. The effect of this is that English Language as a discipline has witnessed dwindling performance in West Africa Certificate Examination (WAEC), National Examination Council (NECO) and other related examination over the years. Teachers of English Language are in no doubt, demoralised by the poor and the dwindling performance of students. The poor state of learning essay writing in our schools has been attributed to many factors. Among the factors that may have accounted for poor performance in the subject are: quality of teaching techniques employed by the teachers, lack of knowledge of subject- matter, lack of interest and other students' related factors. In fact, experts have called for the use of instructional techniques that are student- centered and participatory in nature which will enable the learners take ownership of learning in group context. It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to investigate on the effect of cooperative instructional strategy and senior secondary school academic performance in essay writing in Bayelsa State.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to investigate on the effect of cooperative instructional strategy and senior secondary school students' academic performance in essay writing in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. compare the difference in the mean scores of students taught essay writing with cooperative instructional strategy and those taught essay writing with discussion method.
2. compare the mean performance scores of male and female students in taught essay writing using cooperative instructional strategy and those taught essay writing with discussion method.

Research Questions

The following research questions are posed to guide the study:

1. what is the difference in the mean scores of students taught essay writing with cooperative instructional strategy and those taught essay writing with discussion method?

2. what is the difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught essay writing using cooperative instructional strategy and those taught essay writing with discussion method?

Research Hypotheses

Two (2) null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study.

H0₁. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students taught essay writing with cooperative instructional strategy and those taught essay writing with discussion method.

H0₂. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught essay writing with cooperative instructional strategy.

Research Methodology

The study adopted pre-test post-test quasi- experimental research design. The population of the study comprised of all 19,282 senior secondary two (SS2) students in the 319 public senior secondary schools in Bayelsa State. A sample of 100 senior secondary two (SS2) students participated in this study made up of 58 males and 42 females. The sample size of 100 students participated in the study because two (2) classes were used made of experimental and control group of 50 each. This is carried out by drawing one (1) local government area by simple random sampling. The names of the eight (8) local government areas were written in pieces of paper and one (1) of it was drawn without replacement. Thereafter, a stratified random sampling technique was used to group the number of schools and students from the different educational zones in the local government area for the study. Meanwhile, the final result was two co-educational public secondary schools and sample size of 100 students was drawn for the study. The face and content validity of the instruments were validated by two experts in the Department of Foundations, Arts and Social Science Education, Federal University Otuoke. The reliability of the instrument was correlated using Pearson product moment correlation and the reliability coefficient of 0.76 was obtained. However, the test instrument was given to the two groups as pre-test. Thereafter, the experimental group was treated. The student in the experimental group was exposed to lesson developed using cooperative learning strategy. Then, the same test items was reshuffled and administered as post-test in order to find out the academic performance of the students. The mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels.

Results

Table 1: Mean, standard deviation of students taught essay writing using cooperative instructional strategy and those taught with the discussion method.

Method	N	Pre- test		Post – test		Mean Difference	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Cooperative learning	50	16.70	4.91	69.20	10.37	52.50	
Discussion method	50	10.40	5.34	41.90	9.84	31.50	

Table 1 revealed that students taught with cooperative instructional strategy had a mean score and a standard deviation (\bar{x} = 16.70 and SD = 4.91) during the pre-test while students that were taught with discussion method had a mean and standard deviation (\bar{x} = 10.40 and SD = 5.34). After post-test, students taught with cooperative instructional strategy had a mean and standard deviation (\bar{x} = 69.20 and SD = 10.37) while those taught with discussion method had a mean score and standard deviation (\bar{x} = 41.90 and SD = 9.84). The mean difference of the students taught with cooperative instructional strategy is 52.50 while the students taught with discussion method have a mean difference of 31.50. Therefore, it means that cooperative instructional strategy is more effective than discussion method in the performance of students in essay writing.

Table 2: Mean, standard deviation of male and female students taught essay writing using cooperative learning strategy.

		Pre- test		Post – test		Mean Difference
Gender	N	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	26	16.70	4.91	69.20	10.37	52.50
Female	24	20.50	4.76	72.70	8.28	52.20

Table 2 revealed that male students taught with cooperative instructional strategy had a mean score and a standard deviation (\bar{x} = 16.70 and SD = 4.91) during the pre-test while female students taught with cooperative instructional strategy had a mean score and a standard deviation (\bar{x} = 20.50 and SD = 4.76). After post-test, male students taught with cooperative instructional strategy had a mean and standard deviation (\bar{x} = 69.20 and SD = 10.37) while the female students taught with cooperative instructional strategy had a mean and standard deviation (\bar{x} = 72.70 and SD = 8.28). The mean difference of the male students taught with cooperative instructional strategy is 52.50 while the female students had a mean difference of 52.20. Based on the post test scores, it implies that both male and female student perform almost at equal level, although there is a slight difference in favour of male.

Table 3 Summary of ANOVA of students taught essay writing with cooperative instructional strategy and those taught essay writing with discussion method.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	19220.355 ^a	2	9610.177	97.874	.000
Intercept	29592.654	1	29592.654	301.383	.000
Pretest	588.105	1	588.105	5.989	.016
Method	10642.436	1	10642.436	108.387	.000
Error	9524.395	97	98.190		
Total	337325.000	100			
Corrected Total	28744.750	99			

Table 3 showed an ANOVA showing the difference in the mean scores of students taught essay writing with cooperative instructional strategy and those taught with discussion method. This analysis showed that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement score of students taught essay writing with cooperative instructional strategy and those taught essay writing with discussion method. Thus the null hypothesis was rejected ($p= 0.001, F (1, 97) = 108.387$).

Table 4: Summary of ANOVA of male and female students taught essay writing with cooperative instructional strategy.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	8577.994 ^a	2	4288.997	20.630	.000
Intercept	19384.948	1	19384.948	93.240	.000
Pretest	8577.744	1	8577.744	41.258	.000
Gender	.076	1	.076	.000	.985
Error	20166.756	47	207.905		
Total	337325.000	50			
Corrected Total	28744.750	49			

Table 4 showed an ANOVA showing the difference between the mean scores of male and female students taught essay writing with cooperative instructional strategy. This analysis showed that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female students taught essay writing with cooperative instructional strategy. Thus the null hypothesis was accepted ($p= 0.985, F (1, 97) = 0.001$).

Discussion of Findings

Students Performance in Essay writing using Cooperative Instructional Strategy and Discussion method

The data presented in Table 1 showed that the students taught with cooperative instructional strategy performed better than students taught with discussion method. The implication of this finding is that students found cooperative instructional strategy more effective and active than discussion method in improving their academic performance in essay writing. The findings showed that cooperative instructional strategy has great effect on students' performance is similar to the finding Kolawole (2017) who in their study found out that cooperative instructional strategy significantly improved students' learning and also have a positive effect on the motivation and strategy of students.

Male and Female students' Performance in Essay writing using Cooperative Instructional Strategy and Discussion method

The findings of this study revealed that male students performed better than the female students in essay writing although; there is a slight mean difference in favour of the male students. Meaning that

gender has no influence on students' achievement in essay writing; therefore, the observed difference in favour of female students early identified occurred as a result of chance. The study has proven that gender does not influence students' achievement in essay writing when taught with cooperative instructional strategy. This shows that cooperative instructional strategy is not gender biased in teaching of essay writing as pointed out by Kolawole (2017).

Conclusions

The research work was specifically designed to investigate cooperative instructional strategy and senior secondary school students' performance in essay writing in Bayelsa State. Therefore the findings of this study showed that cooperative instructional strategy significantly improved students' learning ability. Similarly, the finding revealed that there is no gender difference in cooperative learning strategy.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Teacher preparation intuitions should incorporate class wide cooperative instructional strategy in the relevant areas of their curriculum units and expose both the pre-service and in service teachers to these techniques of teaching and learning.
2. The curriculum developers should consider adopting cooperative instructional strategy to prescribe activities for content delivery in English language.
3. School administrators should organize seminar and workshop to sensitise the teachers on the teaching and learning techniques available in the 21st century. This will help to arouse students' interest to put in their best.

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